

RESPONSES TO CONFLICT SITUATIONS IN SCHOOL ORGANIZATION AS CORRELATES OF TEACHER'S PERFORMANCE, SATISFACTION AND COMMITMENT

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ABSTRACT

In the educational process, the teacher has an account for success, or failure in the teaching and learning process. Being the frontliners in the educational process, the teachers are the most holistically taxed persons in school. The administrators should distribute work equally to avoid stressful circumstances that could hinder teachers' job performance, job satisfaction and job commitment. The study utilized descriptive-correlation research design with survey questionnaire. The respondents of the study consisted of 119 teachers of Dapdapan District, Division of San Pablo City. Based on the perceived responses to conflict situation in terms of dimensions of behavior are significantly related to job performance, job satisfaction, and job commitment. Likewise, conflict situations in terms of modes for conflict-handling are also significantly related to job performance, job satisfaction, and job commitment. The parameters on dimensions of behavior and modes of conflict-handling have a direct contribution to the job performance, job satisfaction and job commitment of the teachers. The results of the study served as a basis and guide for the teachers to increase the level of job performance, job satisfaction and job commitment. School management may use the results as basic information and suggestion that can be used to create policies on issues of human resource development, especially conflict management in the work environment.

Keywords: frontliners, job performance, job satisfaction, job commitment